

Deliverable D2

Title

Validation report which details the advanced models developed to describe a) static and continuous and b) dynamic force transfer standards taking into account sensitivity stability, temperature and other parasitic influences on the measurement uncertainty (target uncertainty is 1 % up to 100 Hz and 2 % between 100 - 1000 Hz)

EMPIR Grant Agreement number

18SIB08

Project short name

ComTraForce

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Leading partner

Jonas Sander, Davood Mirian (PTB)

Due date

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Submission date

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